

**СУЧАСНІ ПЕРЕКЛАДАЦЬКІ ТРАНСФОРМАЦІЇ:
ТВОРИ ЛЕСІ УКРАЇНКИ ІТАЛІЙСЬКОЮ МОВОЮ
(НА МАТЕРІАЛІ ІНТЕРВ'Ю ІЗ СУЧАСНОЮ ПЕРЕКЛАДАЧКОЮ В. ДУНАС) /**

**MODERN TRANSLATIONAL TRANSFORMATIONS:
WORKS BY LESYA UKRAINKA IN ITALIAN
(BASED ON AN INTERVIEW WITH THE CONTEMPORARY
TRANSLATOR V. DUNAS)**

Mariia DRUZHYNETS, Professor, PhD
(“Ilya Mechnikov” National University of Odesa, Ukraine)

mriiad68@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8232-0216>

Received: June 1, 2025 | Reviewed: June 3, 2025 | Accepted: June 5, 2025

UDC 81 | DOI from Zenodo

The article is dedicated to the invaluable heritage of Lesya Ukrainka as a figure of Ukrainian national memory, in particular, her contributions to translation. The purpose of the article is to present the translation transformations of Lesya Ukrainka and her works. The object of the study is Italian translations of Lesya Ukrainka's works (based on an interview with the contemporary translator Vira Dunas) and scholarly sources dedicated to translations of the poetess's works. The subject of the study is the peculiarities of the translation of Lesya Ukrainka's poetic works into Polish and Italian and the translation legacy of Lesya Ukrainka in the Crimean period. Lesya Ukrainka's work and translation techniques that can be used to facilitate the transition from original units to translation units have attracted the attention of

Polish (J. Lobodowski, S. Trowokhleb) and Italian (V. Dunas, L. Pompeo) scholars, which are discussed in the article. Lesya Ukrainka's translation legacy of the Crimean period is extremely valuable. The poetess's translation activity and translations of her works are one of the ways in which Ukrainian and foreign intellectuals (people) get acquainted with the best that mankind has created in art, since it was created by the most talented representative not only of her generation in Ukrainian literature, but also among women writers in the world.